

The floating ball with some exercises

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1. Introduction:

We assume the densities of the ball and the liquid are constant. The lift and gravitational force on a floating ball are in equilibrium. The lift force can be calculated by using the pressure integration of half the ball's surface. In equating the gravitational force, we obtain a reduced polynomial of degree 3. Interesting for the reader is the surprising simple form of the solution, however, there are two cases to be distinguished. The choice of the correct unique solution is also interesting.

2. Description:

A ball is floating in a liquid.

It is valid: $\varphi_K < \varphi_F$.

φ_K = density of the ball
 φ_F = density of the liquid
 R = radius of the ball
 T = depth of the ball
 M = midpoint of the ball
 P = pressure

2 cases:

a) midpoint of the ball above the surface

$h =$ height of the midpoint M above the surface. $h \geq 0$

$r =$ integration variable $r \in [0, R]$

depth:

$$T(r) = \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} - h$$

$$P(r) = T(r) \cdot \varphi_F \cdot g$$

$F_{\uparrow} =$ upwards force on the ball

$F_{\downarrow} =$ downward force on the ball

$$F_{\uparrow} = 2\pi \cdot \int_0^{\sqrt{R^2 - h^2}} r \cdot P(r) dr = 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \int_0^{\sqrt{R^2 - h^2}} r \cdot (\sqrt{R^2 - r^2} - h) dr$$

$$F_{\downarrow} := g \varphi_K \cdot \frac{4}{3} \cdot \pi R^3$$

Floating equals equilibrium:

$$F_{\uparrow} = F_{\downarrow}$$

$$\frac{4}{3} \cdot g \varphi_K \pi R^3 = 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \int_0^{\sqrt{R^2 - h^2}} r \cdot (\sqrt{R^2 - r^2} - h) dr$$

h is unknown. This equation must be used to get h . With that, $h \in [0, R]$.

b) midpoint of the ball under the surface

$h =$ depth of the midpoint M under the surface $h \geq 0$

depth:

$$T(r) = h + \sqrt{R^2 - r^2}$$

$r =$ integration variable $r \in [0, R]$

$$P(r) = T(r) \cdot \varphi_F \cdot g \quad r_1^2 = R^2 - h^2$$

$$F_{\uparrow} = 2\pi \cdot \int_0^R r \cdot P(r) dr = 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \int_0^R r \cdot (h + \sqrt{R^2 - r^2}) dr$$

In this case, we must take into account the liquid above the ball inside the cylinder.

$V_z =$ volume of the cylinder

$$V_z = \pi R^2 h$$

$V_{ks} =$ volume of the spherical layer

$$V_{ks} = \frac{\pi h}{6} \cdot (3R^2 + 3r_1^2 + h^2) \quad r_1 = \sqrt{R^2 - h^2}$$

e.g. Bronstein [1] chapter 2.6.2.4 p.200

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\downarrow} &= \frac{4}{3} \cdot \rho_K g \pi R^3 + g \varphi_F \cdot (V_z - V_{ks}) \\ &= \frac{4}{3} \cdot \rho_K g \pi R^3 + g \varphi_F \cdot \left(\pi R^2 h - \frac{\pi h}{6} \cdot (3R^2 + 3r_1^2 + h^2) \right) \end{aligned}$$

With that: $F_{\uparrow} = F_{\downarrow}$

h is unknown. We determine h with $F_{\uparrow} = F_{\downarrow}$.

With that, $h \in [0, R]$.

3. Integration:

We must determine for both cases:

$$\int r \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} dr$$

see Bronstein [1] chapter 1.1.3 3. p.44 Nr.158

$$\int r \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2} dr = -\frac{1}{3} \cdot (R^2 - r^2)^{1.5}$$

control test through differentiation:

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(-\frac{1}{3} \cdot (R^2 - r^2)^{1.5} \right) = -\frac{1.5}{3} \cdot (R^2 - r^2)^{0.5} \cdot -2r = r \cdot \sqrt{R^2 - r^2}$$

The antiderivative is confirmed.

4. Determination of the polynomials:

case a):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{4}{3} \cdot g \rho_K \pi R^3 &= 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \left[-\frac{1}{3} \cdot (R^2 - r^2)^{1.5} - \frac{hr^2}{2} \right]_0^{\sqrt{R^2 - h^2}} \\ &= 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{3} \cdot h^3 - \frac{h \cdot (R^2 - h^2)}{2} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot R^3 \right) \\ &= 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{3} \cdot h^3 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot hR^2 + \frac{h^3}{2} + \frac{R^3}{3} \right) \\ &= 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \left(\frac{h^3}{6} - \frac{R^2 h}{2} + \frac{R^3}{3} \right) \end{aligned}$$

it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_K \cdot \frac{2}{3} R^3 &= \left(\frac{h^3}{6} - \frac{R^2 h}{2} + \frac{R^3}{3} \right) \cdot \varphi_F \\ \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \cdot 4R^3 &= h^3 - 3R^2 h + 2R^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$0 = h^3 - 3R^2h + 2R^3 - \frac{4 \cdot \varphi_K R^3}{\varphi_F} \quad (1)$$

$$h \in [0, R] \quad \varphi_K < \varphi_F$$

case b):

$$F_{\uparrow} = F_{\downarrow}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\uparrow} &= 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \left[\frac{h^2}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \cdot (R^2 - r^2)^{1.5} \right]_0^R \\ &= 2\pi g \varphi_F \cdot \left(\frac{hR^2}{2} + \frac{R^3}{3} \right) \\ = F_{\downarrow} &= \frac{4}{3} \varphi_K g \pi R^3 + \varphi_F \cdot \left(\pi R^2 h - \frac{\pi h}{6} \cdot (3R^2 + 3r_1^2 + h^2) \right) \\ r_1^2 &= R^2 - h^2 \end{aligned}$$

we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_F \cdot \left(hR^2 + \frac{2R^3}{3} \right) &= \frac{4}{3} \cdot \varphi_K R^3 + R^2 h \varphi_F - \frac{\varphi_F h}{6} \cdot (6R^2 - 2h^2) \\ 0 &= \frac{\varphi_F h^3}{3} + (R^2 \varphi_F - \varphi_F R^2 - \varphi_F R^2) \cdot h + \frac{4}{3} \cdot \varphi_K R^3 - \frac{2}{3} \cdot \varphi_F R^3 \\ 0 &= \frac{\varphi_F h^3}{3} - \varphi_F R^2 h + \frac{4}{3} \cdot \varphi_K R^3 - \frac{2}{3} \cdot \varphi_F R^3 \\ 0 &= h^3 - 3R^2 h + 4 \cdot R^3 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 2R^3 \\ 0 &= h^3 - 3R^2 h + 2R^3 \cdot \left(2 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1 \right) \quad (2) \\ h &\in [0, R] \end{aligned}$$

5. Determination of the solutions:

case a):

$$0 = h^3 - 3R^2h + 2R^3 - 4 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \cdot R^3 \quad \text{with (1)}$$

$$h \in [0, R] \quad \varphi_K < \varphi_F$$

This is the reduced form:

$$h^3 + ph + q = 0$$

as to method, see Bronstein [1] chapter 2.4.2.3. p.131,132

$$p = -3R^2 \quad (3)$$

$$q = 2R^3 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{q}{2}\right)^2 \\ &= (-R^2)^3 + \left(R^3 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}\right)\right)^2 = -R^6 + R^6 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}\right)^2 \\ &= R^6 \cdot \left(-\frac{4\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} + \frac{4\varphi_K^2}{\varphi_F^2}\right) = 4 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \cdot R^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1\right) < 0 \end{aligned}$$

With that, $D < 0$.

$\Rightarrow$ There are 3 real solutions.

case b):

$$0 = h^3 - 3R^2h + 2R^3 \left(\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1\right) \quad \text{with (2)}$$

$$p = -3R^2 \quad (5)$$

$$q = 2R^3 \cdot \left(\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{q}{2}\right)^2 \\ &= -R^3 + R^6 \cdot \left(\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1\right)^2 = R^6 \cdot \left(4 \cdot \left(\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}\right)^2 - 4 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}\right) \\ &= 4R^6 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \left(\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1\right) < 0 \end{aligned}$$

With that, there are 3 real solutions.

to case a):

see Bronstein [1] chapter 2.4.2 3 p.132

$$\varrho = \sqrt{\frac{-p^3}{27}} \quad \cos \varphi = -\frac{q}{2\varrho}$$

because of (3),(4):

$$\varrho = \sqrt{\frac{+27 \cdot R^6}{27}} = R^3$$

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{2R^3 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}\right)}{2R^3} = 2 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1$$

to case b):

see Bronstein [1] chapter 2.4.2.3. p 132

with (5):

$$\varrho = \sqrt{\frac{-p^3}{27}} = \sqrt{\frac{+27 \cdot R^6}{27}} = R^3$$

with (6):

$$\cos \varphi = -\frac{q}{2\varrho} = \frac{-2R^3 \cdot \left(2 \cdot \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1\right)}{2R^3} = 1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$$

to case a) and b):

see Bronstein chapter 2.4.2.3. p.132

In both cases is $D < 0$. One of the 3 solutions is the searched for $h \in [0, R]$.

$$y_1 = 2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{\varrho} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3}\right)$$

$$y_2 = 2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{\varrho} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right)$$

$$y_3 = 2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{\varrho} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)$$

with $\sqrt[3]{\varrho} = R$

Now we must decide, if $h = y_1$ or y_2 or y_3 .

to case a): $0 \leq \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \leq 0.5$

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1 \quad \cos \varphi \in [-1, 0] \quad \Rightarrow \quad \varphi \in \left[\frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\right] \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\varphi}{3} \in \left[\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{3}\right]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} &\in \left[\frac{3\pi}{2}, \frac{5\pi}{3} \right] \\ \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) &\in [0, 0.5] \\ \Rightarrow y_3 &= 2R \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) \in [0, R] \end{aligned}$$

y_3 is in the correct interval.

to case b): $0.5 \leq \frac{\rho_K}{\rho_F} \leq 1$

$$\cos \varphi = 1 - \frac{2\rho_K}{\rho_F} \quad \cos \varphi \in [-1, 0]$$

With that, by analogy as in case a):

$$y_3 = 2R \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) \in [0, R]$$

y_3 is in the correct interval, as well.

In case b) the ball is more immersed in the liquid than in case a). $0.5 \leq \frac{\rho_K}{\rho_F} \leq 1$ is valid for case b) and $0 \leq \frac{2\rho}{\rho_F} \leq 0.5$ for case a).

to case a): $0 \leq \frac{\rho_K}{\rho_F} \leq 0.5$

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{2\rho_K}{\rho_F} - 1 \quad \cos \varphi \in [-1, 0] \quad \Rightarrow \quad \varphi \in \left[\frac{\pi}{2}, \pi \right] \quad \frac{\rho}{3} \in \left[\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{3} \right]$$

$$\frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{2\pi}{3} \in \left[\frac{5\pi}{6}, \pi \right] \quad \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \in [-1, -0.86]$$

$$\Rightarrow y_2 = 2R \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right)$$

is no solution to interval $[0, R]$

$$\frac{\rho}{3} \in \left[\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{3} \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} \right) \in [0.5, 0.87]$$

$$\Rightarrow y_1 = 2R \cos \left(\frac{\rho}{3} \right)$$

is no solution to interval $[0, R]$ for $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \leq 0.5$ unless $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 0$, in this case $y_1 = R$ follows.

to case b): $0.5 \leq \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \leq 1$

$$\cos \varphi = 1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \quad \cos \varphi \in [-1, 0]$$

With that, as in case a) $\frac{\varphi}{3} \in [\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{3}]$. We obtain:

y_2 is not a solution for $[0, R]$.

y_1 only has for $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 1$ a solution $y_1 = R$, otherwise y_1 is no solution to $[0, R]$.

to case a) and b):

$$h = y_3 = 2R \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)$$

$$\text{with } \cos \varphi = \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1 \quad \text{for } \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \in [0, 0.5]$$

$$\text{and } \cos \varphi = 1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \quad \text{for } \frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \in [0.5, 1]$$

is the searched solution. $h \in [0, R]$

The simple form of the solution is surprising. I have not seen this solution in any publication. This chapter shows that the problem of floating ball possess a simple solution.

Exercises:

1. A wooden ball with the radius of 4cm is floating in the water (density = $0.9982 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ at 20 degree Celsius). The density of wood is $0.4 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$. How much does the midpoint of the ball tower above the water?

2. In quicksilver a nickel ball with the radius of 6cm is floating. The densities

of quicksilver and nickel are $13.546 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ respectively $8.8 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$. How deep is the ball's midpoint in quicksilver?

3. A ball with unknown material is floating in water. This ball measures 36cm. h shall be 4cm. Which density does the ball have?
For the density of water see exercise 1.

4. A ball of an unknown material is floating in milk. The ball has a diameter of 6cm. It is valid $h = 2.5\text{cm}$. The density of milk is $1.032 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$. What is the density of this ball?

Solutions of the exercises:

To exercise 1:

The ball's radius is $R = 4\text{cm}$. It is valid that $\varphi_K = 0.4 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ and $\varphi_F = 0.9982 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ at 20 degree Celsius. We ask for h .

$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$ is in the interval $[0, 0.5]$. With that it is valid:

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1$$

We get $\varphi = 1.77 \text{ rad}$.

We go on with:

$$h = 2R \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right)$$

It follows that $h = 0.53\text{cm}$.

To exercise 2:

The ball's radius R is 6cm. The densities of nickel and quicksilver are $\varphi_K = 8.8 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ and $\varphi_F = 13.546 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$. We search to h .

$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$ is in the interval $[0.5, 1]$. It follows:

$$\cos \varphi = 1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$$

The calculation leads to $\varphi = 1.8747$ rad.

We use the formula:

$$h = 2R \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)$$

This leads to $h = 1.21$ cm.

To exercise 3:

We infer the data:

$R = 18$ cm and $h = 4$ cm

$\varphi_F = 0.9982 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ is the density of water at 20 degree Celsius.

φ_K is searched.

We use the formula:

$$h = 2R \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3}\right)$$

We transform:

$$\cos\left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3}\right) = \frac{h}{2R}$$

$$\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} = \arccos\left(\frac{h}{2R}\right)$$

$$\frac{\varphi}{3} = \arccos\left(\frac{h}{2R}\right) - \frac{4\pi}{3}$$

At last:

$$\varphi = 3 \cdot \left(\arccos\left(\frac{h}{2R}\right) - \frac{4\pi}{3} \right)$$

We get $\varphi = -8.188$ rad.

There are now two possibilities:

The first possibility is, if $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$ is in interval $[0,0.5]$, the equation:

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1$$

With transformation we obtain:

$$\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = \cos \varphi + 1$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = \frac{\cos \varphi + 1}{2}$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 0.336 \in [0, 0.5]$$

$\varphi_K = 0.335 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ is the first solution.

The second possibility is to apply the equation

$$\cos \varphi = 1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$$

if $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$ is in the interval $[0.5, 1]$.

We solve:

$$\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 1 - \cos \varphi$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = \frac{1 - \cos \varphi}{2}$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 0.6639 \in [0.5, 1]$$

With that, the second solution is $\varphi_K = 0.663 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$.

We see that there are two different solutions.

To exercise 4:

The ball's radius R is 3cm.

The density of milk is $\varphi_F = 1.032 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$.

At $h = 2.5\text{cm}$ we ask to φ_K .

This leads to the following formula:

$$h = 2R \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} \right)$$

Transformation to φ :

$$\frac{\varphi}{3} + \frac{4\pi}{3} = \arccos \left(\frac{h}{2R} \right)$$

$$\frac{\varphi}{3} = \arccos\left(\frac{h}{2R}\right) - \frac{4\pi}{3}$$

At last:

$$\varphi = 3 \cdot \left(\arccos\left(\frac{h}{2R}\right) - \frac{4\pi}{3} \right)$$

With the calculation we get $\varphi = -9.1433$ rad.

First possibility:

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} - 1$$

for $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \in [0, 0.5]$

Now we solve the term to φ_K :

$$\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = \cos \varphi + 1$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = \frac{\cos \varphi + 1}{2}$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 0.0197 \in [0, 0.5]$$

It follows $\varphi_K = 0.02 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ as first solution.

Second possibility:

$$\cos \varphi = 1 - \frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F}$$

for $\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} \in [0.5, 1]$

Solving to φ :

$$\frac{2\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 1 - \cos \varphi$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = \frac{1 - \cos \varphi}{2}$$

$$\frac{\varphi_K}{\varphi_F} = 0.9803 \in [0.5, 1]$$

We obtain $\varphi_K = 1.012 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{dm}^3}$ as second solution.

References

- [1] I.N.Bronstein, K.A. Semendjajew "Taschenbuch der Mathematik"
22. edition, Teubner Verlagsgesellschaft Leipsic 1985
- [2] Harald Schröder "The floating ball and the suspended hollow ball" Wis-
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